

TEMPORAL CHANGES IN FARM AND NON-FARM WAGES IN CENTRAL PROVINCE OF INDIA

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Abstract

The present study has been conducted to study temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages in central province of India. Time series data on farm and non-farm wages from 2012-13 to 2021-22 was collected from secondary sources. Temporal changes in wages were analysed through simple tabular analysis by calculating percentage change in wages over base year for two periods of five years each and overall, ten-year period. Study carried on farm wages for ploughing, sowing, harvesting operations and non-farm wages of blacksmith and carpenter of Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra. The findings reveal that, in overall period study, both farm and non-wages have experienced positive temporal changes in all three states of central province of India. In most of labour categories, percentage change in wages in period-I was higher as compared to period-II.

Keywords: Temporal change, Farm wage, non-farm wage

Introduction

Agriculture played a vital role in the context of employment and livelihood of rural population of India because more than 50 per cent of work force depend on agriculture and over 70 per cent rural population depend on agriculture for livelihood. Understanding wage data help in assessing the economic development of both the agricultural and non-agricultural sector, which are key components of India's economy. Labour was one of important factor of production in agriculture and their wage was main constituent part of cost of cultivation. So rural wages data plays a vital significance in terms of planned development of agriculture sector and rural India. Wage data was critical for conducting many costs of cultivation studies. So, study of "Temporal change in farm and non-farm wages in central province of India" provide a crucial information about wages which would help in development of farmer and reducing cost of production, improve their income and provide valuable input for policymakers in formulating diverse agricultural development policies.

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Material And Methods

The study mainly focused on wages of farm and non-farm labour. The state wise, average daily wages of male and female farm labour for ploughing, sowing and harvesting, and skilled non-farm labour wage for blacksmith and carpenter were taken from various secondary sources. The present research was mainly focused on the three states of central provinces of India, namely Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra. The study was conducted for period from 2012-13 to 2021-22, which was based on the secondary data collected from various sources like Agricultural wages in India (AWI), Agricultural Situation in India (ASI) published by Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmer Welfare, Government of India and Rural Wage Rate published by Labour Bureau of India,

Table 1.1 Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Chhattisgarh

Sr. No	Category	Gender	Daily wages of labour in rupees				% Change in wages		
			2012-13	2016-17	2017-18	2021-22	P- I	P- II	Overall
1	Ploughing	Male	181.75	263.86	268.15	365.85	45.18	36.43	101.29
		Female	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-
2	Sowing	Male	101.03	174.53	181.01	224.68	72.75	24.13	122.40
		Female	82.18	146.01	147.45	195.50	77.67	32.58	137.88
3	Harvesting	Male	97.78	156.21	153.70	219.50	59.75	42.80	124.47
		Female	92.06	141.29	134.43	189.72	53.47	41.13	106.09
	Non-farm wages of								
4	Blacksmith	Male	162.22	255.93	263.26	319.29	57.76	21.28	96.82
5	Carpenter	Male	199.58	313.39	320.95	406.93	57.02	26.79	103.89

Note: P-I: Period between 2012-13 to 2016-17, P- II: Period between 2017-18 to 2021-22 and Overall: Period between 2012-13 to 2021-22, NA: Not Available

During overall period, wages for all the categories of labour has been increased considerably over period of time. In farm wages, for male labour highest percentage increase in wage was observed for harvesting (124.47%) and lowest for sowing (101.29%). For female farm labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for sowing labour (137.88%) and lowest for harvesting labour (106.09%). In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages of carpenter (103.89%) was higher as compared to blacksmith (96.82%).

Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Madhya Pradesh

Table 1.2 Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Madhya Pradesh

Sr. No	Category	Gender	Daily wages of labour in rupees				% Change in wages			
			2012-13	2016-17	2017-18	2021-22	P- I	P- II	Overall	
1	Ploughing	Male	127.78	208.86	219.92	254.57	63.46	15.75	99.23	
		Female	159.81	158.23	165.11	163.29	-0.99	-1.11	2.17	
	Sowing	Male	125.29	192.96	208.29	234.13	54.02	12.41	86.88	
		Female	109.82	180.72	189.96	207.34	64.57	9.15	88.81	
	3	Harvesting	Male	133.30	204.87	214.89	246.46	53.69	14.69	84.89
			Female	115.61	186.12	195.03	218.18	60.98	11.87	88.71
	Non-farm wages of									
4	Blacksmith	Male	146.05	256.97	276.64	330.43	75.95	19.44	126.25	
5	Carpenter	Male	161.42	272.36	288.15	345.53	68.73	19.91	114.06	

Note: P-I: Period between 2012-13 to 2016-17, P- II: Period between 2017-18 to 2021-22 and

Overall: Period between 2012-13 to 2021-22

According to the data presented in Table 1.2 during period- I, wages for all the categories of labour have been increased considerably over period of time, except wage for ploughing of female farm labour. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for ploughing (63.46%) and lowest for harvesting (53.69%). For female farm labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (64.57%) and wage for ploughing (-0.99%) had decreased. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wage of blacksmith (75.95%) was higher as compared to carpenter (68.73%). During the period I, the percentage increase in wages were higher as compared to the period II for all categories of labour.

During period II, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time, except wage for ploughing of female farm labour. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for ploughing (15.75%) and lowest for sowing (12.41%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for harvesting (11.87%) and wage for ploughing (-1.11%) of female had decreased. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages of carpenter (19.91%) was higher as compared to blacksmith (19.44%).

During overall period, wages for all the categories of labour have been increased considerably over period of time. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for ploughing (99.23%) and lowest for harvesting (84.89%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (88.81%) and lowest for ploughing (2.17%). In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages of blacksmith (126.25%) was higher as compared to carpenter (114.06%). Male workers consistently earned higher wages compared to female workers across most activities and

Table 1.3 Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Maharashtra

Sr. No	Category	Gender	Daily wages of labour in rupees				% Change in wages		
			2012-13	2016-17	2017-18	2021-22	P- I	P- II	Overall
1	Ploughing	Male	206.05	273.05	286.30	355.69	32.51	24.24	72.62
		Female	127.15	170.47	195.39	230.84	34.07	18.14	81.55
2	Sowing	Male	181.58	250.25	248.45	335.12	37.82	34.88	84.54
		Female	112.15	165.34	174.83	238.17	47.43	36.24	112.37
3	Harvesting	Male	190.38	249.37	277.58	337.70	30.99	21.66	77.38
		Female	122.46	169.26	196.51	250.87	38.21	27.66	104.85

Pradesh

The Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Madhya Pradesh state was presented in Table 1.2. Wages were depicted according to different categories of labour and gender. Result found that both farm and non-farm wages has been increased considerably in all study periods for all different categories of labour in Madhya Pradesh except wage for ploughing of female labour in period I and period II.

time periods.

Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Maharashtra

The Temporal changes in farm and non-farm wages of Maharashtra state were presented in Table 1.3. Wages are depicted according to different categories of labour and gender. Result found that both farm and non-farm wages has been increased considerably throughout the all-study periods for all different categories of labour in Maharashtra.

According to the data presented in Table 1.3 during period-I, wages for all the categories of labour have been increased considerably over period of time. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (37.82%) and lowest for harvesting (30.99%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for sowing (47.43%) and lowest for ploughing (34.07%). Percentage increase in female labour wages were higher than the male wages in their respective category of labour. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages of blacksmith (43.77%) was higher as compared to carpenter (41.69%). During the period I, the percentage increase in wages was higher as compared to the period II for all categories of labour.

During period II, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time. In farm wages, for male labour, highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing (34.88%) and lowest for harvesting (21.66%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for sowing (36.24%) and lowest for ploughing (18.14%). Percentage increase in female wages were higher than the male wages in their respective category of labour. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wage for blacksmith (21.64%) was higher as compared to carpenter (19.17%).

	Non-farm wages of								
4	Blacksmith	Male	209.32	300.95	310.25	377.39	43.77	21.64	80.30
5	Carpenter	Male	236.37	334.90	345.43	411.64	41.69	19.17	74.15

Note: P-I: Period between 2012-13 to 2016-17, P- II: Period between 2017-18 to 2021-22 and

Overall: Period between 2012-13 to 2021-22

During overall period, wages for all the categories of labour have been considerably increased over period time. In farm wages, for male labour highest percentage increase in wage was observed for sowing labour (84.54%) and lowest for ploughing labour (72.62%). For female labour, highest percentage increase in wage observed for sowing labour (112.37%) and lowest for ploughing labour (81.55%). In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wages of blacksmith (80.30%) was higher as compared to carpenter (74.15%). Male workers consistently earned higher wages compared to female workers across most activities and time periods. Percentage increase in female wages was higher than the male wages in their respective category of work during all three periods.

Over 10-years, highest temporal change in wages was observed in wages for sowing (137.88%) of female labour among both farm and non-farm wages in Chhattisgarh experienced. In Madhya Pradesh highest temporal change in wages was observed in wages of blacksmith (126.25%) among both farm and non-farm wages. In Maharashtra also highest temporal change in wages was observed in wages for sowing (112.37%) of female labour among both farm and non-farm wages. Results of study were similar to previous studies carried by Brajesh (2006), Mukhesh et. al (2009), Nagaraj et. al (2014), Yashwanth and Arnab (2019), and Sant Kumar et. al (2020), where it was proved that both farm and non-farm wages have shown significant positive change over time.

Conclusion and Implications

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the farm and non-farm wages of three states in central province of India have been increased considerably during all study periods except wage of female labour for ploughing during period I and period II of Madhya Pradesh state, where slight decrease in wages was observed. Percentage increase in wages during period I was higher as compared to period II in all 3 states for all categories of labour. Both farm and non-farm wages in Maharashtra and Madhya Pradesh were higher as compared to wages in Chhattisgarh. In farm wages, percentage increase in female wage was higher than male wage in their respective category in most of study periods. In case non-farm wages, percentage increase in wage of blacksmith was higher as compared to percentage increase of wages of carpenter during most study periods.

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